

POSSIBILITY OF USING RADIO MODEMS IN CONDITIONAL DISPOSABLE OCEANOGRAPHIC SONDES

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Introduction. When solving the problem of operational data collection and measurement of the physical parameters of the water area there is a need to create sonde of conditional use.

Main part. The creation of low-cost sonde of conditional use and operational channel of communication with the base station is offered.

The structural structure of the proposed measurement system is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Structure of the measurement system based on the RM sonde

The measurement system includes: a single measurement sonde (RIZ), a radio receiving station (RRS). Radio modem (RM) is included in RIZ, intended for realization of a two-way communication with RRS via radio channel and GPS/GLONASS logger.

The RRS includes a radio modem for two-way communication with the RIZ; a PC for controlling the measurement system, recording incoming data, and their subsequent processing.

The communication of the oceanographic sonde is carried out by means of a radiomodem.

Selection of the radiomodem type was made according to the following main criteria:

- communication range should be not less than 2.0 km;
- minimum power consumption;
- Small dimensions and low cost;
- high sensitivity;
- frequency range and output power should not require agreement on their use.

Structural and functional construction of RIZ depends on the selected types of GPS systems and radiomodems (transceivers). The main criteria for selecting the type of GPS system (module, logger) were:

- high sensitivity of the receiver;
- low consumption;
- frequency of coordinates update should be not less than 1 Hz;
- high accuracy of positioning;
- hot start time not more than 10 seconds;
- low cost and availability of its purchase.

Current probe position can be determined by using loggers Russian global satellite system GLONASS or American global positioning system (GPS), as well as a combined GLONASS combined GLONASS/GPS loggers.

Nowadays the world market offers a great variety of GLONASS and GPS systems that can determine the coordinates of objects with a sufficiently high spatial and temporal resolution with a frequency of coordinate determination up to 4 Hz and with an accuracy up to 1.5 m in space. They are cheap, small in size, and have sufficiently low power consumption.

In accordance with the selected types of radio modems and GPS/GLONASS loggers, a functional diagram of the electronic block of RIZ, which is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - Functional diagram of the RIZ electronic unit

The RIZ includes the following nodes:

- microcontroller (1), designed to control the operation of the electronic block of RIZ according to a specified program;
- Radiomodem (2), designed to transmit data to the shore or ship RPS and receive commands from the RPS;
- measurement module (3);
- autonomous power supply (4) battery designed to power MC and RM;
- flash drive (5) for storing measurement data;
- the antenna unit (6), designed to house the RM antenna and GPS/GLONASS logger.

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